

Sustaining agriculture and pastoralism in mountainous regions

Actions to keep mountain farms viable while safeguarding soils, water and biodiversity.

IMPLEMENTATION CONSTRAINTS AND CO-BENEFITS

Mountain agriculture and livestock farming keep upland landscapes productive and rich in biodiversity, but they are simultaneously under pressure from land abandonment, rising costs, labor shortages, extreme weather events, and increasing erosion. In Greece (e.g., Karpenisi, Samothraki, Crete, Andros), the sustainability of mountain ecosystems depends on healthy pastures, access to water, and the maintenance of terraces and landscape infrastructure. Soil and water protection at the farm level, together with rational/controlled grazing, reduces degradation and helps maintain the yields of mountain agriculture. Key soil protection interventions include controlled grazing, protection of riparian zones, restoration of stone-built terraces and dry-stone walls, ground cover and cover crops in mosaic farmland plots and small-scale water collection/storage. Agroforestry and nature-based solutions (hedgerows, buffer strips, restoration of wetlands/erosion hotspots) strengthen resilience and ecosystem services. Digital tools (GIS/remote sensing) support targeted interventions

and monitoring, while local collaborations and short value chains can reward good practices and help keep young people in mountain areas.

Figure 1 Example land-use and soil risk layers for a mountain catchment (photo S. Tampekis).

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Summary: By combining controlled grazing, restoration of terraces/dry-stone walls, protection of riparian zones, and targeted Nature-based Solutions (NbS) with GIS-based monitoring, we reduce erosion and risks while sustaining production and farm income in mountain systems.

Example: On Andros Island, the LIFE TERRACESCAPE project revived and restored terraces/dry-stone walls as “green infrastructure,” delivering benefits such as reduced soil erosion and flood risk, and improved infiltration and groundwater recharge.

KEYWORDS

mountain farming; pastoralism; agroforestry; silvopastoral systems; nature-based solutions; rotational grazing; terraces; water harvesting; socio-ecological resilience

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